

Erroneous data in a meta-analysis on vitamin C and the common cold by Saeed (2023)

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Comment on:

Haitham Saeed, Mohamed EA Abdelrahim.
A Meta-Analysis of the Effectiveness of Vitamin C in the Prevention and Treatment of Childhood Upper Respiratory Tract Infections.
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On the first line of Figure 2 [1], Saeed states that the mean number of colds in the Coulehan (1974) trial was 19 in the vitamin C group (N = 190) and 23 in the placebo group (N = 192). However, these are not the mean numbers of colds, but they are the total number of colds in the group. The correct means are 0.1 (= 19/190) and 0.12 (= 23/192) [2]. Thus, the data on the first line of Figure 2 [1] are incorrect. The correct comparison between the vitamin C and placebo groups of the Coulehan (1974) trial gives RR = 0.83 (95%CI: 0.47 – 1.48) [3] which indicates no difference between the groups, in contrast to Saeed's calculation [1].

On the second line of Figure 2 [1], Saeed states that the mean number of colds in the Ludvigsson (1977) trial was 1.63 in the vitamin C group and 1.36 in the placebo group. However, these are not from 304 and 311 participants as stated by Saeed [1]. The 1.63 and 1.36 are from Ludvigsson's "pilot study" which had only 78 and 80 participants [4]. Thus, the data on the second line of Figure 2 [1] are also incorrect.

On the third line of Figure 2, Saeed gives incorrect SD valued for the Bancalari (1984) trial [5]. The correct comparison between the vitamin C and placebo groups of the Bancalari (1984) trial gives RR = 0.94 (95%CI: 0.67 – 1.32) [3] which indicates no difference between the groups, in contrast to Saeed's calculation [1].

The fourth line of Figure 2 gives data for the Cohen (2004) trial. However, the Cohen trial is not a vitamin C trial, as participants were administered also Echinacea and propofol [6].

The fifth line of Figure 2 gives is data for the Garaiova (2021) trial. However, the Garaiova trial is not a vitamin C trial, as participants were administered also probiotics [7].

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

If the scientific question is, whether vitamin C has effects on the common cold, then the included trials should be limited to trials in which the only difference between the trial groups is vitamin C [3].

In the abstract, Saeed writes “On average, vitamin C-treated children had fewer upper respiratory tract infection bouts, their illness lasted shorter (MD -0.84; 95% CI -1.47 to -0.20, P = 0.009)” [1]. This is based on the erroneous data in Figure 2 [1]. In our Cochrane review, we showed that there is no evidence that vitamin C has effect on common cold incidence in the general population, with RR = 0.97 (95%CI: 0.94 – 1.00) [3]. Nevertheless, there is strong evidence that common cold episodes are shorter and less severe when taking vitamin C [3].

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